

Towards Collaborative and Privacy-Preserving Predictive Modelling in Manufacturing: Benchmarking Federated Learning Strategies

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ABSTRACT

This research addresses the critical challenge of implementing predictive quality estimation in manufacturing environments where data privacy and intellectual property concerns hinder centralized data pooling. The primary objective is to introduce novel consensus-based Federated Learning (FL) approaches and benchmark them against traditional centralized and isolated learning paradigms and existing FL approaches using CNC milling datasets to classify process conditions. Performance is evaluated using Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) and recall of the minor class to account for data imbalances and the need to detect rare anomalies. Experimental results on representative machine data demonstrate that the proposed method achieves robust performance, while maintaining a high level of data confidentiality suitable for deployment in industrial maintenance environments. This study demonstrates that federated architectures can enable robust cross-site collaboration in quality control and be effectively extended to predictive maintenance and asset health monitoring. Validating these privacy-preserving strategies encourages broader industrial adoption of data-driven approaches, ensuring reliability across distributed manufacturing assets while maintaining strict data sovereignty.

Keywords

Federated Learning, Smart Manufacturing, XGBoost, Consensus Ensemble, Process Condition Monitoring, Transfer Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Industrial machine manufacturers are increasingly expected to deliver not only high-quality hardware, but also data-driven services such as predictive maintenance, process optimization, and performance monitoring. A key enabler for these services is process knowledge derived from operational data of similar machines already deployed at customer sites. Over time, such data captures valuable insights into machine behavior, wear patterns, and optimal operating conditions. Transferring this knowledge to newly delivered machines can significantly reduce commissioning time, stabilize early operation, and improve overall lifecycle performance.

In practice, however, the systematic reuse of process knowledge across machines remains challenging. Industrial customers typically enforce strict non-disclosure agreements (NDAs) that prohibit the sharing of raw machine data. As a result, machine manufacturers are unable to centrally collect or directly reuse operational data from different customers [1], [2], despite clear potential benefits for maintenance and reliability engineering.

A commonly applied workaround is to train machine learning models individually for each machine or customer installation. While this approach is compliant with data protection and contractual constraints, it suffers from limited data availability and poor generalization, particularly for new machines during early lifecycle phases. From an industrial perspective, this often leads to unstable model performance and limits the economic value of data-driven maintenance solutions [3].

Federated Learning (FL) has recently gained attention as a promising approach to address these challenges. By enabling collaborative model training without exchanging raw data, FL aligns well with industrial confidentiality requirements [4]. Nevertheless, standard FL implementations still require the sharing of model parameters or gradients, which may expose sensitive information about machine behavior, production processes, or customer-specific operating strategies.

To address these limitations, this paper proposes a FL approach based on compiled model artifacts or local inference endpoints sharing, which enables the transfer of process knowledge across machines while minimizing the amount of shared information and avoiding known data protection trade-offs associated with conventional FL.

2. STATE OF THE ART

FL enables multiple data sources with local models to train a global model iteratively based on an aggregation of hyperparameter or gradients from local models during each training iteration [5]. The aggregation is often conducted by averaging the model parameters, known as federated averaging (FedAvg) [6]. FL has since been applied in manufacturing, particularly in fault detection and diagnosis [7], [8]. FL has become widely accessible as several open-source frame-works support the implementation of FL approaches and workflows nowadays, such as Flower [9]. Despite its advances, the adoption of FL in real-world maintenance scenarios remains limited. Central concerns are the constraint on uniform model architectures across all client and server devices [10] and information leakage risks through data reconstruction from shared model updates [11] [12]. To mitigate the risk of data reconstruction, various privacy-enhancing techniques have been proposed, including differential privacy, secure aggregation, and encryption-based methods [13]. However, these techniques often introduce additional complexity, computational overhead, or performance degradation [14] [15], which can be problematic in industrial environments with limited resources or strict real-time requirements.

A FL aggregation techniques that have been specifically developed

for tree-based models, is FedXGBBagging for local XGBoost (eXtreme Gradient Boosting) models [16]. This is particularly important because in industrial practice, tree-based models such as Random Forests or Gradient Boosting methods are frequently applied due to their robustness, interpretability, and relatively low requirements regarding feature preprocessing and strong performances in various maintenance-related tasks [17], [18]. In Gradient Boosting, weak learners, which are often individual decision trees with only one split, are sequentially combined. The contribution of each new tree is evaluated by the gradient of its loss function in respect to the outcome of the previous model. A prominent gradient boosting algorithm is XGBoost, which supports distributed and parallel computing to ensure optimal scalability [19]. Another aggregation method for gradient-boosted decision trees is bagging in which multiple classifiers are trained in parallel on resampled versions of the training data. Averaging the outputs of these base learners has been shown to reduce variance and improve generalization performance [20]. However, not implemented in a FL approach, these models rely on centralized data aggregation and are therefore infeasible for cross-customer deployment.

To avoid raw data sharing in centralized models and avoid model parameter sharing in FL, decentralized consensus-based approaches have been proposed. Consensus in models means a group decision-making process considering the predictions of all group members [21]. Examples include a Test-Time Collective Prediction, introduced by Mendler-Dünner et al. [22], that aggregates model predictions at inference time using trust scores derived from locally estimated performance and a DeGroot consensus mechanism. Similarly, Magureanu and Usher [23] proposed a decentralized ensemble learning paradigm in which only initial model predictions are exchanged to reach consensus on a test input. While these decentralized consensus-based approaches eliminate the need for raw data or parameter sharing, they are inherently limited to prediction-level aggregation and do not enable iterative model refinement. While such approaches can achieve coordination between machines, they do not result in a single global model that can be directly deployed or reused for new machines.

To mitigate these limitations, Federated Distillation (FD) has been proposed as an alternative, where only prediction outputs such as logits or probability vectors are exchanged among clients. While FD reduces communication costs and privacy risks, it often relies on a public reference dataset with a distribution similar to that of the clients, which may pose intellectual property concerns [10]. FD has been applied to bearing fault diagnosis by Liu et al. [24].

From an industrial maintenance perspective, existing approaches reveal several gaps for global model representation of process knowledge. To bridge this gap, this study introduces novel consensus-based ensemble learning frameworks that combines decentralized consensus formation with iterative local model training. By leveraging consensus margins as a learning signal, the proposed approach enables continuous model improvement without sharing raw data or model parameters. Instead, only compiled model artifacts or local inference endpoints are shared.

3. METHODS & MATERIALS

3.1 Learning Strategies

This section presents the four used consensus-based learning strategies for distributed training of Gradient Boosting models, each employing knowledge distillation to achieve model agreement

while limiting data exposure. All approaches maintain data locality while enabling collaborative learning through iterative soft target refinement. In practice, cross-predictions between peers are obtained through compiled model artifacts or local inference endpoints, so that neither readable model parameters nor raw samples need to leave their origin facility.

3.1.1 Foundational Framework: Knowledge Distillation for Consensus

The proposed consensus strategies share a common foundational framework based on knowledge distillation. Consider a federated setting with K clients (in our case $K = 3$ CNC machines), where each client k possesses a local dataset. At each training iteration t , each k maintains a local Gradient Boosting model $f_k^{(t)}$. The consensus probability for sample i on client k is computed as the mean prediction across all models:

$$p_{\text{consensus},i}^{k,t} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{j=1}^K f_j^t(x_i^k)$$

The soft target for training incorporates both the true label and the consensus prediction through a convex combination controlled by the distillation parameter $\alpha \in [0, 1]$:

$$\tilde{y}_i^{k,t} = \alpha \cdot y_i^k + (1 - \alpha) \cdot p_{\text{consensus},i}^{k,t}$$

When $\alpha = 1$, the model trains purely on ground-truth labels (standard supervised learning). When $\alpha = 0$, the model learns exclusively from peer predictions (pure distillation). Each model is trained incrementally using the binary cross-entropy (log-loss) objective L_{BCE} , which naturally accommodates soft targets $\tilde{y} \in [0, 1]$.

3.1.2 Standard Distillation Ensemble

The Standard Distillation Ensemble serves as the reference consensus approach, implementing the foundational framework without additional modifications. The training objective for client k at iteration t is:

$$\min_{f_k} \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} L_{BCE}(\tilde{y}_i^{k,t}, f_k(x_i^k))$$

The prediction threshold is optimized post-training to maximize the F1 score on the training set, making this approach particularly suited for scenarios where balanced precision and recall are desired.

3.1.3 Class-Balanced Distillation

The Class-Balanced Distillation approach extends the standard framework by introducing sample weights that compensate for class imbalance. This is a critical consideration in the considered scenario, where the minority class (abnormal process conditions) comprises only ~4% of samples. For each client k , sample weights are computed using inverse class frequency:

$$w_i^k = \frac{n_k}{(2 \cdot n_{c(y_i^k)})}$$

where n_c^k denotes the number of samples belonging to class c in client k 's dataset. This weighting scheme ensures that each class contributes equally to the total loss, regardless of its prevalence. The prediction threshold is optimized for the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC).

3.1.4 Uncertainty-Weighted Distillation

The Uncertainty-Weighted Distillation approach introduces an adaptive weighting mechanism that emphasizes samples where the ensemble exhibits high prediction disagreement. The underlying hypothesis is that samples with high inter-model variance represent challenging or ambiguous cases that warrant increased attention during training.

At each iteration t , the prediction variance for sample i on client k is computed across all models:

$$\sigma_i^{(k,t)2} = \left(\frac{1}{K}\right) \sum_{j=1}^K ((f_j^t(x_i^k) - p_{\text{consensus},i}^{k,t}))^2$$

The uncertainty is defined as the standard deviation, and sample weights are computed as:

$$w_i^{k,t} = 1 + \gamma \cdot \sqrt{(\sigma_i^{(k,t)2} + \epsilon)}$$

where $\gamma = 5.0$ is a scaling factor controlling the influence of uncertainty, and $\epsilon = 10^{-6}$ ensures numerical stability. This formulation assigns higher weights to samples where models disagree, forcing the ensemble to focus on resolving conflicts. As training progresses and models converge toward consensus, the variance decreases, and the weighting scheme naturally transitions toward uniform weighting.

3.1.5 Agreement-Regularized Distillation

The Agreement-Regularized Distillation employs a custom objective function that explicitly penalizes deviation from the consensus prediction. This approach adds an explicit regularization term to the loss function. The custom objective combines the standard log-loss with a quadratic penalty for disagreement:

$$L_{\text{reg}}(\tilde{y}, p, p_{\text{consensus}}) = L_{\text{BCE}}(\tilde{y}, p) + \lambda \cdot (p - p_{\text{consensus}})^2$$

where $\lambda = 0.1$ controls the regularization strength. This dual-objective formulation creates a tension between fitting the possibly noisy soft targets and maintaining agreement with the current consensus. The regularization term acts as a smoothing mechanism, preventing individual models from deviating too far from the collective prediction.

3.2 Datasets

To evaluate various data availability scenarios and learning strategies, a real-world dataset from three distinct CNC milling machines with 1702 data points is employed, where each data point comprises three acceleration recordings (x-, y-, z-direction). Thereof, the total acceleration can be calculated from the acceleration in the three spatial directions. Taking only the overall acceleration into account, allows the problem to be viewed as a univariate time series mining task. The process condition as a label allows binary classification. First, without applying data preprocessing, the raw acceleration data is embedded into fixed-dimensional vectors using feature extraction. Tsfresh (version 0.21.0) [25] is applied for feature extraction and the resulting features were reduced to 26 features that have proven useful in similar scenarios [26]. The separation of trainings and test dataset is implemented in a way that the process condition classes are proportionally distributed between these two. Based on that, a subset of the training dataset is generated to represent a scenario in which each operation type is only executed on a single machine and data from the other two machines with this type of operation is eliminated. Operations were distributed to the machine that executed the most processes of this operation type. The allocation

of operation to one machine is mapped in the description of the datasets. This reflects a situation commonly encountered in industrial practice, where setup times and wear-related effects determine the allocation of processes to machines. The reduced trainings dataset under consideration contains 643 datapoints. By doing this only for the training dataset the global model will be tested on machine-process-combinations that are not in the training dataset. This should simulate the performance of the global model on existing and new machines. The training set can be partitioned in the three original machines to create a scenario of data silos. The training/test dataset and all used Scripts for data preparation and experiment execution are available on Zenodo [27].

3.3 Experimental Setup

The dataset is imbalanced with a class ratio of 1:24, where a naive majority-class classifier would reach approximately 96% accuracy while entirely missing the minority class. Therefore, the MCC is used as the primary metric. It incorporates all four quadrants of the confusion matrix into a single value from -1 to $+1$, penalizes all error types symmetrically, and only achieves high values when both classes are classified well. A naive majority-class classifier yields an MCC of 0. Additionally, Recall for the minority class 0 is evaluated, as missing defective process conditions can be cost-critical, and the F1-score serves as a broadly used comparison metric. MCC is defined as:

$$MCC = \frac{TP \cdot TN - FP \cdot FN}{(TP + FP) \cdot (TP + FN) \cdot (TN + FP) \cdot (TN + FN)}$$

with true predicted positives as TP, true predicted negatives as TN, false predicted positives as FP, and false predicted negatives as FN. The experimental evaluation employs stratified 5-fold cross-validation to ensure robust performance estimation across all approaches. Each fold maintains the original class distribution, with models trained on data from three CNC machines and evaluated on a held-out test partition. All experiments use a fixed random seed.

Eight learning approaches are compared. Baseline-1 trains a centralized XGBoost classifier on pooled data from all machines, while Baseline-2 trains three independent models, one per machine, each evaluated on the complete test set. Approaches 1 through 4 implement the proposed consensus-based distillation strategies described in the previous section. FedXGBoost-TreeAgg Approach employs federated XGBoost with tree bagging using the Flower framework, where local trees are aggregated via concatenation across 30 server rounds. FedXGBoost-CNNMeta-2 Approach implements HFedXGBoost [28] with a CNN meta-learner that combines predictions from locally trained Gradient Boosting models through a 1D convolutional architecture.

All XGBoost models share common hyperparameters: maximum tree depth of 6, learning rate of 0.1, and binary logistic objective. The centralized and per-machine baselines train 90 boosting rounds directly. The consensus approaches perform 30 distillation iterations, where each iteration adds one tree per client, yielding comparable model complexity. The distillation parameter α is optimized for each approach (1: 0.5, 2: 0.9, 3: 0.2 and 4: 0.7). For Approach 4, the agreement regularization strength λ equals 0.1. The federated approach (FedXGBoost-TreeAgg) executes 30 server rounds with one local boosting round per client. HFedXGBoost (FedXGBoost-CNNMeta) trains 30 local trees per client, followed by 10 federated rounds of CNN training with 10 local epochs each; the CNN uses 64 channels and a learning rate of 0.001 as defined by [28].

Figure 1: 5-fold cross-validation results across all eight prediction approaches, displaying mean values for F1-score, Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) and minority class recall with 95% confidence intervals (95% CI)

Decision thresholds are optimized on training data. This optimization ensures fair comparison by allowing each approach to operate at its optimal operating point rather than using the default 0.5 threshold. The implementation leverages XGBoost’s dual interfaces: the scikit-learn [29] compatible XGBClassifier for the baseline approaches, and the native `xgb.train()` interface for approaches requiring incremental tree construction (1–4, FedXGBoost-TreeAgg).

Approach 4 employs a custom objective function implemented as gradient and Hessian arrays to incorporate the agreement regularization term. For FL, the Flower framework orchestrates client-server communication, with tree aggregation performed via JSON serialization of XGBoost’s internal model representation. The HFedXGBoost approach combines XGBoost for local tree training with PyTorch for the CNN meta-learner, using federated averaging to aggregate CNN weights across clients.

In this experimental setup, data and models are stored on one machine for simulation purposes. In real-world scenarios, additional setup for confidential data/model sharing between actors via compiled model artifacts (e.g. via treelite [30]) or a data inference APIs is needed.

4. RESULTS

Figure 1 presents the 5-fold cross-validation results across all eight approaches, displaying mean F1-score, mean MCC, and mean minority class recall with 95% confidence intervals (95% CI).

F1 score exhibited uniformly high mean values across all methods (range: 0.979–0.996), providing limited discriminative power between approaches. This pattern is consistent with class imbalance, where high F1-score can be achieved by a model biased toward the majority class. Centralized baseline (Baseline-1) achieved an mean MCC of 0.642 and a mean Recall(0) of 0.485, establishing a competitive but imbalanced benchmark, the model correctly identifies only approximately half of class-0 instances despite its high mean F1 (0.989).

Per-machine baselines (Baseline-2) showed high inter-machine

variability. Machine 1 yielded the strongest per-machine result (mean MCC = 0.799, mean Recall(0) = 0.768), while Machines 0 and 2 performed substantially worse (mean MCC = 0.080 and 0.244, mean Recall(0) = 0.033 and 0.180, respectively). Individual machines provide training distributions of unequal utility, per-machine models did not generalize reliably in isolation.

Consensus distillation approaches (1–4) consistently outperformed both baselines across MCC and Recall(0) on average with smaller ranges in 95% CI. Approach 3 (Uncertainty-Weighted Distillation) achieved the highest mean MCC (0.905) and tied with Approach 1 (Distillation, F1-optimized) for highest mean Recall(0) (0.900). Approach 4 (Agreement-Regularized Distillation) ranked closely behind (mean MCC = 0.889, mean Recall(0) = 0.871), while Approach 2 (Balanced Distillation, MCC-optimized) yielded the weakest results on average within this group (MCC = 0.760, Recall(0) = 0.747). All four approaches improved in mean values over Baseline-1 by 0.118–0.263 MCC points and over 0.4 in Recall(0).

Federated approaches occupied an intermediate position. FedXGBoost-TreeAgg surpassed Baseline-1 in mean MCC (0.736 vs. 0.642) but did not reach the 95% CI of the distillation group. FedXGBoost-CNNMeta recorded a mean MCC of 0.654, which is only marginally above Baseline-1, though its mean Recall(0) of 0.711 represents a notable improvement over the centralized model. Both federated bagging methods exhibited higher variance in MCC and Recall(0).

Overall, the results indicate that approaches combining knowledge sharing across machines through soft-target distillation (Approaches 1–4) yield the most balanced detection performance, whereas purely federated aggregation strategies provide more modest gains over the centralized baseline under the conditions evaluated.

5. DISCUSSION

The experimental results provide several insights into the design of privacy-preserving learning strategies for manufacturing quality control. Additionally, they underscore that models trained on

individual machines cannot reliably generalize. Individual machines encounter only a subset of operating conditions and fault patterns, leading to models that overfit to local data distributions especially when representation of minority class samples is insufficient. This finding reinforces the industrial motivation: isolated learning may not be merely suboptimal, but potentially dangerous when deployed for safety-critical process monitoring.

Overall, the consensus-based approaches successfully bridge the gap between centralized and isolated learning, achieving performance comparable to the centralized baseline with iterative knowledge transfer mechanisms while preserving raw data/label locality. By incorporating peer predictions as soft targets, each local model gradually learns decision boundaries that generalize beyond its own data distribution. In Approach 1-4, the distillation parameter α balances trust in local ground truth against consensus information, preventing any single model from dominating the ensemble while still anchoring predictions to true labels.

The FedXGB Bagging approach presents less prediction performance than the consensus-based approaches. The performance gap between Approaches 1–4 and the FedXGBBoost variants is interpretable in terms of the information transmitted during collaboration. Federated tree aggregation and CNN meta-learning operate on model outputs or parameters, without explicit supervision about the confidence or uncertainty of individual predictions. Soft-target distillation, by contrast, transmits richer distributional information. In class-imbalanced settings where minority instances are sparse, additional signals may be disproportionately valuable.

FedXGBBoost-CNNMeta achieves higher mean Recall(0) (0.711) than FedXGBBoost-TreeAgg (0.522), despite lower mean MCC (0.654 vs. 0.676). This suggests the CNN meta-learner shifts the decision boundary toward the minority class at the cost of additional false positives, without improving overall discriminative balance. In operational contexts where the cost of missing a minority-class event is high, such as fault detection, higher Recall(0) may be preferable despite the MCC penalty. Conversely, FedXGBBoost-TreeAgg may be preferred where false positives carry significant cost. This tradeoff highlights that method selection should be guided by application-specific cost structures rather than a single aggregate metric.

From a practical standpoint, the consensus distillation approach offers compelling advantages for industrial adoption. Unlike standard FL, the distillation mechanism exchanges prediction vectors rather than gradient updates or transparent model trees. Enabling cross-predictions in a distributed setting requires distributing either compiled model artifacts, which conceal readable tree parameters from receiving facilities, or exposing local inference endpoints that accept peer data and return predictions only. The approach is architecture-agnostic, allowing heterogeneous client implementations, and produces a deployable ensemble without requiring a central server during inference. These properties align well with industrial requirements for data sovereignty and operational independence.

Several limitations warrant consideration. First, experiments were conducted in a simulated federated environment on a single machine. Real-world deployments would face additional challenges including network latency, client dropout, and asynchronous updates. Second, the dataset represents a specific CNC milling scenario with three machines, generalization to other manufacturing processes and larger client populations requires

further validation. Third, with the class imbalance, performance characteristics may differ under more balanced conditions. Finally, while the distillation mechanism limits exposure compared to gradient or full-tree sharing, residual privacy risks remain: enabling cross-predictions requires either model distribution or data submission to peer facilities, and adversarial clients could potentially extract information from exchanged soft targets or probe distributed model artifacts.

6. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

This paper addressed the practical challenge of transferring process knowledge across industrial machines under strict data sharing restrictions. We presented and evaluated consensus-based distributed learning strategies for training Gradient Boosting models without centralizing data or exchanging visible model parameters. The proposed approaches were benchmarked against both centralized and conventionally distributed training setups.

The results show that some of the proposed consensus-based strategies achieve predictive performance comparable to centralized training and consistently outperform isolated per-machine models and FL approaches. At the same time, the consensus-based approaches avoid typical information exposure risks associated with parameter-sharing FL schemes. This makes them particularly suitable for cross-customer industrial environments governed by NDAs and confidentiality constraints. From an industrial perspective, the presented method enables machine vendors to reuse operational knowledge for newly deployed machines while maintaining customer data sovereignty. This supports faster model ramp-up and more stable early-life condition monitoring without requiring changes to existing contractual data protection frameworks.

Future work should investigate the aggregation of heterogeneous model types within the same consensus framework. This would represent a distinct advantage over established FL approaches. However, further validation on larger and more heterogeneous machine fleets is required to assess scalability, robustness, and operational integration effort in real maintenance environments.

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